

TEACHING UZBEK IN MULTILINGUAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. This article deals with some peculiar properties of teaching Uzbek in multilingual environment, as well as three main directions of teaching Uzbek. Also, corpus-based teaching considered in this article as a modern method of teaching languages in multilingual environment.

Keywords: Language teaching, multilingual environment, modern methods, computer technologies, heritage learners, corpus-based learning.

Multilingualism is the ability of an individual speaker or a community of speakers to communicate effectively in two/three or more languages. Multilingualism is a very common phenomenon all over the world. Teaching Uzbek in multilingual environment has some peculiar properties. At first, teaching Uzbek has three different and at the same time closely connected directions: teaching Uzbek as native language, as official/state language, as foreign language.

Uzbek can be taught in a natural language environment or outside a language environment. In a natural language environment, students can be native speakers, representatives of related languages, or representatives of unrelated languages. They learn the language in educational institutions, in language centers/courses, and they can also learn the language individually during the private lessons. Thus, students of different nationalities, speaking different languages of different levels, can be gathered in one university auditorium. In addition, it is necessary to distinguish between areas of education, such as pedagogy, medicine, architecture, agriculture and so on. In turn, outside Uzbekistan, students of Uzbek language courses are

foreigners, people with Uzbek roots (“heritage learners”), also students who are planning to get married with Uzbeks. All these features of the class where Uzbek is taught create difficulties in planning the process of learning the language. In each case, the educational goals, objectives, program, methods, materials will be different from others.

In this regard, there is a need to find the new effective methods of teaching Uzbek language. There is such a large-scale didactic tool that helps the studying and teaching languages as a linguistic corpus, the creation, development of which is one of the urgent problems of both theoretical and practical linguistics.

N.V. Kozlova under the corpus means an electronic complex of texts in one or several languages, created on the basis of certain parameters. In her opinion, being a collection of texts in written or verbal form, the corpus differs from ordinary texts in that it is digitized, that is, texts are analyzed electronically, have special tags, they are stored electronically, have linguistic annotations that put all this information in order¹.

We believe that the definition given by V.P. Zakharov can be considered the most complete:

Linguistic corpus of texts is a large, electronically presented, unified, structured, tagged, philologically competent array of language data designed to solve specific linguistic problems².

In general, the following qualities are indicated in each description:

1. It is necessary to provide many texts (on the Internet or on disk).
2. The material must be authentic, not edited, it must show the variability of the language units, it is possible to include materials of “live speech”.
3. To carry out linguistic analysis, language units must be tagged.

¹ Козлова Н. В. Лингвистические корпуса: определение основных понятий и типология. Вестник НГУ. Серия: Лингвистика и межкультурная коммуникация. 2013. Т.11 Выпуск 1. – С. 79.

² Захаров В. П. Корпусная лингвистика. СПб., 2005 – С. 3.

4. As a result of the analysis, it should be possible to distribute language material based on various principles (for example, by genre, date of creation of the text, topic, and so on).

So how exactly can Uzbek instructor use the corpus while teaching languages? Corpora can help in the following cases:

- in determining the lexical minimum, i.e. the minimum number of words that students need to know to master the language at a particular level. To understand how necessary is for students to know exactly these words, what is their frequency, which words are outdated and which are considered neologisms;

- in choosing theoretical material for writing textbooks or for a regular lesson. Answer the questions - how important are these grammatical rules, when exactly it is necessary to study which rule, how often there are exceptions to the rules; do the norms of the literary language change, if so, how and for what reason;

- in demonstrating linguistic realities, in order to show how a particular word or phrase actually behaves in life, in which context the studied language units can most often be found, when explaining the valence of words, their compatibility. In demonstrating style differences and syntactic synonymy;

- in teaching a language for special purposes, that is, to know what medical students, engineering students, businessmen and others should pay attention to.

- in using an inductive approach to teaching. Students can make certain conclusions by studying examples of concordance. In some cases, this is much more effective than doing exercises to activate vocabulary or grammar rules or reading artificially created texts.

- in analyzing the teaching process and preparing the lesson plans in order to increase the effectiveness of classes.

Obviously, the quality of a corpus depends on its creators, on the amount of base material, on the time of its creation. Unfortunately, for many years, the national corpus of the Uzbek language did not exist. Only the corpus created in 2012 was available on the Internet. Below is given information about it:

“The Uzbek Web Corpus (uzWaC) is an Uzbek corpus made up of texts collected from the Internet. ... total size 18 million words. A complete set of tools is available to work with this Uzbek corpus to generate:

- word lists - lists of Uzbek words organized by frequency;
- n-grams - frequency list of multi-word units;
- concordance - examples in context”³.

Trial use of this case showed that the creation of the case is a painstaking and large-scale work, the quality of which is influenced by each element of the material. The corpus in question is written in the Uzbek Latin alphabet. In all parts of the corpus, except the frequency list, diacritical marks are not recognized by the computer program. Words containing such sign < ' > are divided into parts and these parts of words behave as separate tokens. For example, when identifying the compatibility of the word "baland", variants that did not exist in the language were encountered. As examples from some context the corpus showed such word collocations as "yi baland", "li baland keldi", "baland ko", and so on. In fact, these should be word combinations "bo‘yi baland", "qo‘li baland keldi", "baland ko'tarmoq". The problem is related to the presence of a special element in the letters o‘ and g‘. Also, the problem will exist if use the Cyrillic alphabet, since in the Uzbek Cyrillic there are also some elements that are not recognized by a computer program. These thoughts, in turn, prove the need to revise and somewhat change the current Uzbek alphabet.

Recently, the academic community was informed about the creation of a new corpus of the Uzbek language, which works in a test mode. Hopefully, that soon both students and teachers can use it to the fullest.

In the world practice of language teaching, corpus methods are recognized as highly effective innovative methods. These methods have aspects of intersubject integration, empirical adequacy, authenticity, flexibility, adaptability, “discovery”

³ uzWaC: Uzbek corpus from the web <https://www.sketchengine.eu/uzwac-uzbek-corpus/>

in language learning. And after all, being familiar with corpuses should be a standard characteristic of both today's language instructors and students.